

Some Interesting Aspects of the Chemistry of Platinum

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PLATINUM is one of the least reactive of metals. It does not tarnish and is insoluble in even the strongest of acids. Simple (hydrated) platinumous and platinumic ions are almost unknown. In spite of these limitations, the chemistry of platinum is extremely varied and interesting and offers a fertile field for investigation. The common oxidation states of platinum are +2 and +4, but compounds are known in which several other oxidation states are shown. Interesting examples are $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3]$ and $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_4]$, in which the metal is formally in the zero oxidation state, and in the first of which the metal has the unusual coordination number of three¹. Even fractional oxidation states exist in such compounds as $\text{Cs}_{1.75}[\text{Pt}(\text{CN})_4] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Rb}_{1.6}[\text{Pt}(\text{CN})_4] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{C}(\text{NH}_3)_3]_2[\text{Pt}(\text{CN})_4] \text{Br}_{0.28} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{K}_{1.84}[\text{Pt}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2]^{2-}$. These are important because of their electronic properties. In compounds such as $\text{Pt}_3\text{Sn}_8\text{Cl}_{20}$ ², it is futile to try to assign an oxidation state.

In this paper, we are concerned chiefly with the coordination compounds of platinum in the +2 and +4 oxidation states. In the former, platinum usually shows a coordination number of four, but in the trigonal bipyramidal ion $[\text{Pt}(\text{SnCl}_3)_5]^{3-}$, the coordination number is five³. Many of the compounds in which the coordination number is four have high catalytic power, especially for hydrogenation. In these complexes, there is one empty p orbital, through which a carbon-carbon double bond can attach itself to the metal.

	5d	6s	6p
$\text{Pt}(\text{I})$	0 0 0 0	— —	— — —
$[\text{PtX}_4]^{2-}$	0 0 0 0	X X	X X —

We have used this catalytic property in the selective hydrogenation of soybean oil, which is a mixture of glycerides of several long chain carboxylic acids, with all of the double bonds in the *cis* configuration :

Most of the soybean oil of commerce goes into food products such as oleomargarine and salad oils. The triply unsaturated linolenic ester, which is present in the oil to the extent of 7-10%, has an unpleasant taste, and many efforts have been made to hydrogenate one double bond in this ester without affecting the other double bonds in the molecule and without hydrogenating the linoleic or oleic esters. Complete saturation must be avoided at all costs, as the saturated esters are hard to digest.

In order to avoid the complication of having three acid chains (perhaps all different) in one molecule, it has been customary in research studies to replace the glyceride unit with methyl groups. My colleagues and I have made extensive studies of the selective hydrogenation of soybean oil, using as the hydrogenation catalyst, a mixture of bis-diphenylphosphine-dichloro platinum(II) and several equivalents of tin(II) chloride, thus generating the complex $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{SnCl}_3)\text{Cl}]$, which, upon hydrogenation, evidently becomes $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{SnCl}_3)\text{H}]^+$. With this catalyst, it is easily possible to hydrogenate *all but one* double bond. When the catalyst is immobilized by attaching it to polystyrene, it is possible to hydrogenate one double bond of the linolenic ester, leaving two, mostly, however, in the *trans*-form. The details of this work have been described recently and need not be repeated⁴. The subject is mentioned here only to call attention to the catalytic power of platinum(II) complexes.

Another important application of platinum complexes is in the treatment of cancer. In 1965, Barnett Rosenberg at Michigan State University observed that *cis*-dichlorodiammine platinum has the ability to inhibit the division of *Escherichia coli* into separated cells, though it does not inhibit the growth of the cells⁵. This led him to the suggestion that this compound might be effective in the treatment of cancer and, indeed, experiment showed this to be correct. The compound is now being used clinically, under the name cisplatin, in the treatment of certain cancers. Needless to say, Rosenberg's exciting discovery has stimulated a great deal of work in this field, and something over

twelve hundred compounds have now been synthesized and tested. Most of these contain platinum, but other metals of the platinum family have been tried too. Cisplatin is not an ideal drug, for it is not as effective as we might wish, it is only very slightly soluble and it is horribly toxic. From the many experiments that have been carried out, certain "rules" have been derived. First, the compound must contain two groups which are tightly bound to the platinum and two which are slowly hydrolyzed off. The tightly bound groups may be ammonia molecules, as in cisplatin, or they may be amine molecules of a wide variety. Evidently there must be at least one hydrogen atom on the ammine nitrogen. Second, the hydrolyzable groups must be displaced slowly. Nitrate groups will not do, for they are hydrolyzed off too rapidly; cyano groups are ineffective because they are not hydrolyzed off at all. Chloro groups are satisfactory, their hydrolysis in the body being somewhat inhibited by the presence of chloride ion in body fluids. Other groups that have been found to be effective include sulphato, gluconurato and pyromellito. Supposedly, the non-ionic cisplatin dissolves to a slight extent in the fatty tissue of the body. It is held there until reaction with water converts it to the ionic aqua complex $cis-[Pt(NH_3)_2(H_2O)_2]^{2+}$ or the hydroxo-aqua complex $cis-[Pt(NH_3)_2(H_2O)(OH)]^+$. These then attach themselves to the strands of the diseased DNA, the nitrogen atoms of the nucleic acid displacing the aqua and/or hydroxo groups. Compounds in which the hydrolyzable groups are *trans* to each other are completely ineffective.

It should be noted in passing that this picture does not tell the whole story, for some compounds that do not resemble cisplatin closely have been found to be effective. Such a one is the dimeric rhodium(II) acetate hydrate, $[Rh_2(CH_3COO)_4 \cdot (H_2O)_2]^{2+}$.

Optical isomers differ not only in the direction in which they rotate the plane of polarized light but also in their reactivity with other chiral substances. This suggests that the enantiomers of platinum compounds might have different effectiveness in the treatment of cancer. Optical activity of a planar platinum complex can be achieved by using an optically active ligand. Rosenberg tried the propylenediamine complex but found little

difference in the effectiveness of the two isomers⁹. Kidani used 1,2-cyclohexanediamine, of which the *trans* form is chiral¹⁰.

He found the *levo-trans* isomer to be more effective than the *dextro-trans* isomer, which, in turn, is more effective than the optically inactive *cis* isomer.

We have applied ourselves to this problem too. The first compounds which we made contained 2,2'-diaminobiphenyl as the ligand.

This compound owes its chirality to the fact that the two phenyl rings cannot lie in the same plane but must be tilted with respect to each other, thus assuming a propellor-like configuration. We did not separate the isomers but submitted the racemic material for testing. It has some effect but not enough to warrant further work. In the mean time we learned that aliphatic groups have been found to be better than aromatic ones, so we prepared the cyclohexane analogue.

The rings in this compound are not planar as they are in the biphenyl derivative, but they still must be held in "tilted" positions and the platinum compound should be optically active. The resolution of this compound is being studied by Dr. Masahide Noji, who prepared the compound in our laboratory and is now continuing the work in Japan.

Currently, we are working on this problem from two angles—altering the nature of the asymmetric ring and increasing the solubility of the complex. In some cases these objectives overlap. We have prepared 1,2-cyclooctanediamine, which is similar to Kidani's cyclohexanediamine, but because of its larger size, should be more flexible. We have considered going the other way too, to the cyclobutanediamine but have not attempted any syntheses. In each case there are symmetrical *cis* and chiral *trans* isomers.

For increase in solubility, we are introducing functional groups, as with the ligands biguanide and 2-hydroxy-1,3-diaminopropane or by making the

complex ionic by using a bidentate, negative ion as the ligand.

The 2,3-diaminopropionic acid complex resembles the ethylenediamine complex, which has been shown to be effective against certain cancers but is insoluble. The presence of the carboxyl group gives good solubility but whether the chirality of the carbon atom will give the two isomers different physiological properties remains to be seen.

Quite a different kind of platinum chemistry is also underway in our laboratory. The famous Russian chemist Chugaev observed that some complexes containing platinum in both the cation and anion undergo an interesting disproportionation reaction when they are heated. Some examples are

experimentally in all cases). If that is the case, we can imagine that there are residual forces between the ligands in each plane and the platinum atoms in the adjoining planes (Fig. 1).

Upon heating, these residual forces may bring about the rearrangement. With the ammonia complex $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_4][\text{PtCl}_4]$, these forces would be weak and in accordance with this, the disproportionation reaction in that case takes place at a much higher temperature than in the other cases.

For the fourth example above, we must have a slightly different picture, for the entire molecule of dithioether migrates from one platinum atom to the next (Fig. 2).

To determine whether the disproportionation takes place in steps Dr. Hideyoshi Morita, working in our laboratory, prepared the ions $[\text{Pt}(\text{Me}_2\text{S})_2\text{Cl}]^+$ and $[\text{Pt}(\text{Me}_2\text{S})_2\text{Cl}_2]^-$. He expected, when he mixed solutions of these, to obtain the salt $[\text{Pt}(\text{Me}_2\text{S})_2\text{Cl}][\text{Pt}(\text{Me}_2\text{S})_2\text{Cl}_2]$. Much to our surprise, he obtained instead the final product of the disproportionation, $[\text{Pt}(\text{Me}_2\text{S})_2\text{Cl}_2]$. If the reaction takes place in steps, the second step must be very rapid. We do not yet know the mechanism of this reaction, but the work is still in progress.

No survey of the chemistry of platinum is complete without mention of the many isopolymeric compounds which it forms. These contain

Chugaev had no way to study the mechanism of these reactions, and we are interested in pursuing this part of the problem. All of the ions concerned, except those in the third example, are planar and are probably stacked, with cations and anions alternating. (This has, however, not yet been proven

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

from two to twenty six atoms of platinum per molecule¹⁵. The most complex compounds which have yet been prepared are $[\text{Pt}_{18}(\text{CO})_{36}]^{2-}$ and $[\text{Pt}_{26}(\text{CO})_{52}]^{10-}$.

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